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Final Brief Report

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Abstract

This Final Brief Report presents the main results and legacy of the GraspOS project, with a focus on the resources, experiences and insights developed to support the ongoing reform of research assessment in Europe. The report provides an overview of the project's outcomes and reflects on how they can be used and interpreted by communities and stakeholders involved in research assessment.

The project addressed the need for transparent, responsible, and context-sensitive evaluation by delivering the GraspOS infrastructure, a suite of open data, tools, services, guidelines and other resources relevant to research assessment along with an EOSC-integrated meta-catalogue, which facilitates their discovery. Additional, key practical outputs include the SCOPE+i Framework, a collection of guides and templates for assessment process design, and

a comprehensive training program featuring an on-demand course on the OpenPlato platform. The report briefly presents the aforementioned project outputs while also synthesising evidence and insights from nine pilot studies conducted across diverse organisational and disciplinary contexts.

By integrating technical solutions with community-driven guidance, GraspOS provides a technical and practical foundation for stakeholders to implement assessment reforms that are consistent with CoARA and the EOSC. This report serves as a legacy document intended to inform future efforts in evolving the global research assessment culture.

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Author List

ORGANISATION	NAME	CONTACT INFORMATION
OpenAIRE	Giulia Malaguarnera	giulia.malaguarnera@openaire.eu
CNR	Lottie Provost	lottiemiaprovost@cnr.it

Contributor List

ORGANISATION	NAME	CONTACT INFORMATION
ARC	Thanasis Vergoulis	vergoulis@athenarc.gr

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Abbreviation List

AI	Artificial Intelligence
CoARA	Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment
CoP	Community of Practice
CRIS	Current Research Information System
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
DECP	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan
DORA	Declaration on Research Assessment
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOSC-A	European Open Science Cloud Association
OA	Open Access
RFO	Research Funding Organisation
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
RRA	Responsible Research Assessment
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This Final Brief provides a clear and accessible overview of the main results achieved by the GraspOS project and presents the key resources and lessons that the project leaves as legacy for future initiatives in research assessment. Prepared for the European Commission and the wider research community, the report summarises in a non-technical way how the project has advanced Responsible Research Assessment (RRA) and supported the transition toward more transparent, inclusive and Open Science-aligned evaluation practices.

The purpose of this document is to outline the project's final outcomes in a concise and understandable manner, ensuring that stakeholders, regardless of their technical background, can appreciate the progress made.

Over its lifetime, GraspOS has designed and developed an open infrastructure that enables the discovery of open data, tools, services, and other resources for responsible, Open-Science-aware research assessment; a comprehensive framework accompanied by practical templates, guides and checklists to support every stage of an evaluation process; a dedicated training course designed to introduce users to the rationale, tools and methods behind assessment reform; and a collection of insights from nine pilot studies that tested a range of research assessment use cases across universities, funders and disciplinary communities. Together, these outcomes demonstrate how responsible and context-sensitive assessment practices can be implemented in real settings and create a solid foundation for future developments in this field.

This Final Brief highlights the significance of these results, while technical specifications and implementation details are to be found in the project's deliverables and are not examined in depth here. This final output reflects the project's commitment to openness and community engagement, and aims to ensure that its work continues to inform and support the reform of research assessment beyond the project's duration.

1. Project overview

GraspOS – *Next Generation Research Assessment to Promote Open Science* – is a Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Action (Grant Agreement No. 101095129) with the overarching aim to extend and better organize the existing landscape of open data, tools, services, guidelines, and other resources that can support a more responsible and transparent system of research assessment crediting Open Science activities (alongside other research contributions). From January 2023 to December 2025, the project has worked to design, develop, and operate the GraspOS infrastructure: an EOSC-integrated meta-catalogue that enhances the discoverability and interoperability of open resources to support policy reforms towards a more responsible, transparent and Open-Science-aligned research assessment.

The GraspOS infrastructure was initialised drawing on existing resources developed by the project technical partners, which were appropriately extended and configured to account for Open Science contributions and to be aligned to modern responsible research assessment practices. Through its nine Pilot studies, the GraspOS project has co-designed, tested and evaluated a range of approaches across universities, funding agencies, and disciplinary communities, based on the aforementioned resources, ensuring that the resulting solutions remain sensitive to organisational and disciplinary diversity. Following the completion of the project, the GraspOS infrastructure aims to become a fully open infrastructure, allowing any resource to be added in accordance with a set of predefined inclusion criteria, which are expected to be published soon after the project's conclusion.

GraspOS serves a wide range of stakeholders. Researchers and research teams benefit from tools that help articulate and present their careers beyond traditional contributions and metrics. Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) and Research Funding Organisations (RFOs) gain practical resources to redesign evaluation procedures in line with evolving policy expectations. Scientometricians, librarians, and research data analysts can leverage a variety of openly available data, tools, and services to conduct analyses and introduce and evaluate new research assessment practices. Research infrastructures and Current Research Information Systems (CRISs) can exploit the project's technical foundations, while stakeholders across the EOSC ecosystem benefit from improved discoverability and interoperability of data, tools, services and guidance relevant to assessment reform.

By providing an open and community-driven suite of resources, GraspOS enables organisations to assess Open Science practices more systematically, reduce uncertainty in adopting new approaches, and align their procedures with emerging European and

international standards. At the same time, the project addresses several key needs expressed by the research community: the urgency to reform how assessment is performed; the need for qualitative, context-aware evaluation supported by richer data and indicators that are being used responsibly; the desire for coherent guidance aligned with ongoing initiatives; the need to strengthen trust in open infrastructures; and the importance of ensuring that resources for Open-Science-aware research assessment are easily discoverable and usable within EOSC.

2. Key results

Over the course of the project, several complementary results came together to support a more open, fair and meaningful way of assessing research. The first was the development of the GraspOS infrastructure¹, a suite of open data, tools, and services, and other resources needed for more informed, responsible, and Open-Science-aware evaluation processes along with a meta-catalogue², which makes it easier to discover and combine them. Alongside this, the project developed the SCOPE+i Framework along with a set of practical resources^{3,4} that help organisations turn principles of responsible assessment into clear, workable steps. Moreover, the project invested in building skills and shared understanding through training activities and a growing community of practitioners. Finally, the project collected evidence and insights from nine pilot studies conducted across diverse organisational and disciplinary contexts. Together, these results show how technical innovation, practical guidance, community engagement and improved representation of research activities can work hand in hand to support assessment reform in real settings.

¹ GraspOS infrastructure: <https://graspos-infra.athenarc.gr/>

² GraspOS meta-catalogue: <https://graspos-infra.athenarc.gr/catalogue/>

³ News item published in graspos.eu:

<https://graspos.eu/graspos-scope-i-resources-to-support-rra-now-available-in-zenodo>

⁴ Zenodo community collecting the SCOPE+i resources:

<https://zenodo.org/communities/graspos-assessment-process-resources/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

2.1. The GraspOS Infrastructure

The project developed an open, federated infrastructure designed to facilitate the discovery of open resources (data, tools, services, templates, and guidance materials) that can catalyse the implementation of policy reforms towards Open-Science-aware responsible research assessment. Figure 1 presents a high-level conceptual architecture of the infrastructure.

Figure 1 GraspOS infrastructure architecture

The architecture of the GraspOS infrastructure mainly consists of a set of core catalogues that collect basic metadata for research assessment resources; a Data Interoperability & Access Layer (DIAL) that improves interoperability across federated data sources; and a web-based front-end that provides access to the core catalogues, enriches their metadata to improve resource discoverability, and supports advanced search capabilities through a meta-catalogue that facilitates the discovery of valuable research-assessment resources. Together, these elements enable users to explore a wide range of resources through a single environment, while preserving a federated and modular approach.

At the centre of this setup is the [GraspOS meta-catalogue](#), which acts as the main entry point for discovering resources that may be useful for research assessment activities. Through the GraspOS meta-catalogue, users can find descriptions of datasets, services, and tools, as well as supporting materials such as templates and guidance documents. Each resource is

presented with clear information on its type, the kind of data or analysis it provides, and its potential use in assessment-related activities.

The GraspOS meta-catalogue enables users to search, browse and filter a range of resources according to different criteria, helping them identify tools and services that match specific interests or analytical needs. It includes services that provide access to data and analytical functionalities which can be reused for bibliometric analyses, disciplinary mapping, monitoring of research outputs and other sector-level explorations. Alongside these, templates and guidance materials are available as practical reference points for organisations and practitioners reflecting on how to approach research assessment.

By bringing these resources together in a single, structured environment, the GraspOS meta-catalogue facilitates access to existing tools and supports their reuse across different contexts. This allows users to move more easily from discovering available resources to selecting and applying those that are most relevant for their own research assessment activities.

Feedback collected across the project through the Pilot studies, the Community of Practice and dissemination activities highlighted the value of testing services and prototypes in real settings. Participants noted that engaging with data-driven tools helped clarify both the potential and the limits of existing data, as well as the challenges of combining quantitative and qualitative information. These experiences supported organisations in reflecting on monitoring approaches and on how Open Science practices could be more meaningfully considered in research assessment.

Across these groups, the infrastructure supports a more informed and flexible use of existing resources, helping different actors engage with research assessment according to their roles and needs. **Researchers** may use its tools to explore how their diverse contributions can be captured. **RPOs** can benefit from improved access to data sources and services that support more nuanced evaluations. **RFOs** can use it to identify tools that aid panel deliberation or the exploration of novel indicators. **Data and service providers** gain clearer expectations about the types of information and interoperability needed to support emerging assessment practices. Across the **EOSC** ecosystem, the infrastructure contributes to shared approaches for openness, metadata consistency and reusable services.

Figure 2 GraspOS infrastructure and catalogue ([link](#))

2.2. SCOPE+i Framework

[The SCOPE+i Framework](#) is one of the project's core results, offering a practical and structured way to design and document research assessment processes that are fair, transparent and aligned with Open Science. Building on the established SCOPE Framework, the project expanded it with a collection of [process-oriented resources](#) such as templates, guides and checklists, alongside light digital services that support the collaborative creation and sharing of assessment plans. Together, these elements help organisations translate responsible assessment principles into concrete steps that can be adapted to their own context.

Throughout the project, users consistently highlighted the value of having clear, ready-to-use materials that bring coherence to what can otherwise be a complex and unfamiliar process⁵. Many emphasised that the framework provided direction, practical guidance and a systematic approach at moments when institutions often struggle with uncertainty. At the same time, the flexibility of the resources allows organisations to tailor procedures while maintaining a shared understanding of good practices.

The SCOPE+i Framework is intended for a wide range of stakeholders.

Researchers benefit from clearer expectations and support in presenting diverse research contributions. **Research-performing organisations** can reuse the materials to establish or refine institutional evaluation procedures. **Funders** gain structured guidance to develop assessment criteria and support panel deliberations. **Assessment experts** and policy specialists can rely on the framework as a common reference, while **data and service providers** can better understand the information needs associated with emerging assessment workflows. The framework also aligns with principles promoted within the **EOSC** ecosystem, supporting interoperability and openness.

Overall, SCOPE+i offers communities a practical, adaptable path toward more responsible and Open Science-aware research assessment.

⁵<https://graspos.eu/report-from-the-graspos-pilot-workshops>
<https://graspos.eu/ssh-pilot-consultation-workshops-2>
<https://graspos.eu/building-roadmaps-for-the-graspos-pilots-identifying-pathways-for-service-inclusion>

	S	C	O	P	E
Guide for assembling an assessment team G	●	●			
Value statement template T	●				
Purpose and context statement template T		●			
Guide on choosing an assessment method G			●	●	
Stakeholder mapping template T	●	●			
Indicators guide 1: Responsible use of indicators G	●	●			
Indicators guide 2: Frameworks and toolboxes for open research G			●	●	
Open Science assessment guide G	●	●			
Guide on the diversity of OS contributions, roles and activities G			●	●	
Guide on promoting OS contributions in a narrative CV G			●	●	
Guide on equity, diversity and inclusion (EDI) in research assessment G	●	●			
Checklist for responsible research assessment C	●	●	●	●	●
Guide for evaluating the assessment process G					●
Guide on principles for responsible research assessment for evaluators and evaluands G			●	●	
Assessment readiness template T	●	●			
Guide for overcoming common obstacles in implementing RRA G			●	●	
Institutional assessment process checklist C			●	●	

G = GUIDE **T** = TEMPLATE **C** = CHECKLIST

Figure 3 SCOPE+i published in [Zenodo](#)

2.3. Training

The project developed a comprehensive training programme designed to help the research community understand and apply responsible and Open Science-aligned research assessment practices. Building on the strong interest shown across Europe, the programme combined a structured [series of training sessions, webinars and demonstrations](#), culminating in the release of a [dedicated online course on the OpenPlato platform](#). Through this mix of live events and on-demand learning, the training offered practical guidance on the principles behind assessment reform, the use of emerging indicators, and the application of the SCOPE+i Framework and the GraspOS Catalogue.

The training responds to a clear need expressed by institutions, funders and researchers for accessible explanations, concrete examples and hands-on support when navigating the shift away from traditional metrics. Many organisations reported uncertainty about how to incorporate Open Science practices into evaluation processes or how to interpret new forms of evidence. The training addressed these needs by offering user-friendly guidance, and demonstrations of tools and services tested during the project. It also created a shared space for dialogue, helping participants build a common understanding of assessment principles and challenges.

Through OpenPlato, the research community can continue to access the course at their own pace, reuse selected modules for local training, and integrate the materials into institutional programmes. In this way, the training ensures long-term accessibility and supports the broader uptake of responsible research assessment practices.

New Course to Rethink Research Assessment

Figure 4 Training Course in OpenPlato launched on December 2025

2.4. Community engagement, Pilots Outcomes, and Reflection from GraspOS experience

A central element of the project was the continuous engagement with the communities that design, carry out and are directly affected by research assessment. This work converged in the publication of the Booklet *Promising Stories from the Pilot studies*⁶, which brings together the experiences of the nine Pilot organisations experimenting with new ways of recognising research contributions. Their narratives show what happens when assessment practices are tested in their own pilot's settings: the opportunities, the challenges, and the very practical questions that arise when moving beyond traditional metrics. Across universities, funders and disciplinary groups, the Pilots demonstrated how essential it is to balance quantitative and qualitative information, to consider local cultures and expectations, and to work with data that is both reliable and interoperable. These stories enrich the more technical outputs of the project by showing what responsible assessment looks like in practice: difficult at times, but collaborative, grounded, and deeply shaped by context.

To support this ongoing learning, the project also created a [Community of Practice](#) where researchers, managers and funders met regularly to exchange perspectives. These conversations were informal in tone but meaningful in substance. Participants shared frustrations with existing systems, reflected on what had worked for them, and explored what responsible assessment might look like in their own environments. A recurring message was the importance of community involvement: reforms are more credible and more sustainable when people have the space to talk openly about what they need and what they are unsure about. Participants also recognised that there is no single model that fits all; instead, having a common language and a set of adaptable tools helps organisations navigate the complexity of their own contexts.

Reflections emerging from these engagement activities echoed this shared understanding. Many highlighted the value of having alternatives to traditional bibliometric tools, and the importance of widening the types of evidence that can meaningfully inform assessment. Others stressed that a real change of the research culture is possible only when diversity, recognising different methods, disciplinary cultures and expectations, is acknowledged as a strength rather than an obstacle. Several stakeholders in Research Assessment practices also

⁶ Provost, L. (2025). Promising stories from the GraspOS Pilot studies. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17789961>

emphasised how helpful concrete examples are in shaping policy and institutional decisions. A consistent takeaway across all discussions was that responsible assessment is not purely a technical shift: it is a cultural one, built through collaboration, openness to experimentation, and steady dialogue over time.

Policy implications arising from this collective work point toward openness, contextualised approaches and alignment with broader European initiatives such as CoARA and EOSC. These aspects are expanded in the dedicated policy brief.

3. Bridging Project Results and Future Uptake

The GraspOS Final Conference, titled [Opening Research Assessment](#), was conceived as a moment to open the project's work to a broader community and to connect its results with ongoing debates, practices and policy developments beyond the project itself.

Held on 12–13 November 2025 in Pisa at the CNR, [the conference marked a key moment of reflection and consolidation for the project](#)⁷. Bringing together researchers, research managers, funders, infrastructure providers and policy actors, the event provided an opportunity to present the project's results and to situate them within the broader international discussion on research assessment reform.

Across two days of presentations, panels and demonstrations, discussions focused on open infrastructures for research assessment, transparency and inclusivity of evaluation processes, and the recognition of diverse research contributions and Open Science practices. The conference highlighted strong alignment between GraspOS outcomes and ongoing policy and community initiatives, including [CoARA](#) and [DORA](#), as well as European priorities under the [ERA Policy Agenda](#).

Importantly, the event offered space to reflect on lessons learned from the Pilot studies and to openly discuss implementation challenges, reinforcing the project's core message: responsible research assessment requires not only technical solutions, but shared understanding, institutional commitment and sustained collaboration. In this sense, the Final

⁷ More information on the GraspOS Final Conference Highlights are written in this news article: <https://graspos.eu/highlights-from-the-graspos-final-conference-opening-research-assessment>

Conference acted as a bridge between project results and their future uptake, confirming the relevance of GraspOS contributions within the evolving European research assessment landscape.

4. References

- Provost, L. (2025). Promising stories from the GraspOS Pilot studies. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17789961>
- GraspOS Training Material: <https://graspos.eu/training-material>
- GraspOS Training Course in OpenPlato <https://openplato.eu/course/view.php?id=549>
- SCOPE+I Framework: <https://zenodo.org/communities/graspos-assessment-process-resources/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>
- GraspOS Catalogue: <https://graspos-infra.athenarc.gr/catalogue/>